

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Apiculture sector policies - positive and negative elements to support healthy market conditions

[version 1; peer review: 3 not approved]

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Abstract

Background

Honey market health indicators, such as production, consumption, and trade balance, exhibit notable variation across countries. Given that policy objectives typically aim to regulate markets either directly or indirectly, it was found pertinent to examine whether correlations can be established between honey market health metrics and policies perceived as beneficial or detrimental to the apiculture sector.

Method

An open, international, web-based survey was designed to gather opinions on policies perceived as positively or negatively influencing the health of the honey market, based on the premise that a healthy honey market is fundamental for a thriving apiculture sector. The survey, created using Google Forms, included only one mandatory question, namely the respondents' country, and allowed participants to list up to three examples each of positive and negative policies. Members of the BeSafeBeeHoney project, COST Action 22105, were encouraged to assist in gathering responses, ideally from beekeepers' associations within their countries, though all responses were welcome.

Results

Sixteen survey responses containing 72 policy examples were collected from 13 countries: Albania, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Denmark, Germany, Kosovo, Italy, Serbia, Spain,

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Slovakia, Türkiye, and the United Kingdom. Of these, one response was gathered via interview. The policy example responses were compiled and organized in a spreadsheet for further grouping and sorting using various criteria. The 13 countries were categorised into three groups based on positive, slightly negative, or negative honey trade balances.

Conclusions

A quantitative analysis of survey responses did not establish a connection between honey trade balances and national policies. Qualitative analyses reflected a general perception of three decisive policy areas, namely i) subsidisation, ii) product classification and labelling, and iii) regulations governing pesticides and veterinarian medicine. Overall, our research highlights challenges within the sector resulting from irregular market mechanisms, with indications that the predominant market channels operate largely beyond public oversight, contributing to concerns about effective regulation and control.

Keywords

Apiculture, policies, market health, honey

This article is included in the [COST Actions gateway](#).

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Background

Honeybees are essential pollinators, with about 75% of major crops relying on pollination, which boosts global crop production by approximately 9%¹. The demand for beehive products, especially honey, is increasing across Europe. This trend is largely attributable to the presence of bioactive compounds and the associated health benefits found in many of these products, including notable anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties.

The apiculture sector within the European Union is currently facing several significant challenges². The total number of beehives declined by 1.2% from 2022 to 2023, primarily due to a reduction in the number of professional producers managing more than 150 hives. Between 2018 and 2022, the average market price for honey decreased from €6.42 to €6.25 per kilogram, largely attributed to increased competition from imported honey of questionable quality². Notably, this decline occurred during a period marked by a general 42% increase in overall food prices³. Imported honey averages just €1.89 per kilogram, and with imports accounting for approximately 37% of EU consumption, the region remains significantly short of self-sufficiency². Nearly 76% of honey imports originate from Ukraine and China².

Concerns about the quality of imported honey are linked to widespread allegations of fraud, particularly adulteration - often involving the blending of honey with inexpensive

syrops - which is facilitated by natural variance in honey's constituents under the EU Honey Directive⁴. Misleading labelling can cause consumers to believe they are purchasing local honey, undermining fair competition and distorting market dynamics. It is estimated that up to 10% of internationally traded honey is adulterated, with rates potentially reaching 30% for imports from certain countries, including China⁵. The European agriculture umbrella organization COPA-COGECA, which also represents beekeeping associations, has described the state of the honey market as alarming⁶.

A healthy market is typically defined by self-sufficiency (production plus imports minus exports greater than or equal to consumption, adjusted for change in storages), which is indicated by a positive trade balance, as well as a profitable and stable production economy where sales prices exceed production costs and the price volatility is minimal³. Table 1 presents examples of honey trade balances for selected countries.

Variations between the reported trade balances, whether derived from Eurostat or Faostat data, suggest that official statistics on the honey market may not be entirely consistent. Also, some discrepancies to honey statistics provided by World Integrated Trade Solutions are observed⁷. Another indication for this is that Denmark in accordance with information provided by the Danish Beekeeper Association's website⁸ produces 3–5,000 tonnes of honey annually, which is two to three times higher than the figures reported by Faostat – see Figure 1.

Table 1. Honey trade balance in 2023 for selected countries, based on Faostat data on export and import as well as population⁹ and compared with Eurostat based data for EU Member States¹⁰. Countries are sorted descending after the Faostat-based trade balance. No statistics exists for Kosovo.

	Faostat data				Eurostat data
	Exports, tonnes	Imports, tonnes	Population, 1,000	Per capita trade balance, kg	Per capita trade balance, kg
Bulgaria	10,991	3,226	6,796	1.14	-0.19
Serbia (incl. Montenegro)	1,510	377	6,773	0.17	
Türkiye	9,386	15	87,271	0.11	
Albania	8	50	2,812	-0.02	
Slovakia	1,694	1,814	5,518	-0.02	-0.17
Spain	27,352	31,005	47,912	-0.08	-0.18
Bosnia and Herzegovina	7	469	3,185	-0.15	
Denmark	2,826	4,154	5,948	-0.22	-0.28
Italy	5,730	24,361	59,499	-0.31	-0.08
Croatia	739	2,775	3,896	-0.52	-0.19
Germany	18,021	64,469	84,548	-0.55	-0.43
UK	2,268	50,917	68,683	-0.71	

Figure 1. Per capita annual production (dark orange) and consumption (light orange) (kg) of honey in selected BeSafeBeeHoney countries (Based on data of Faostat, 2023⁹, production figures for Italy based on Faostat data for 2022⁹).

Imprecise statistics regarding honey may result from the fact that a significant portion is produced by hobbyists and sold informally outside of regulated market channels. According to information provided by the Danish Beekeepers Association⁸, approximately 55% of the honey production is attributed to hobby beekeeping, and similar trends are likely present in other countries. Such circumstances can significantly impede the effectiveness of standard market mechanisms and may create opportunities conducive to unlawful activities.

The BeSafeBeeHoney^{11,12} project is a COST Action that receives financial support from the European Union. It operates through international collaboration among researchers and various beekeeping stakeholders to improve the European honey sector, focusing on nutrition, health, abiotic and biotic stressors, and pollination within agrarian ecosystems. The project also includes market analysis and translates technical findings from its different components into policy recommendations.

Behind the general honey market situation in the EU are wide variations between countries, suggesting that the apiculture sector enjoys better market conditions and more favourable policies in some countries than others, since in their essence, policies are made for regulation of markets, directly or indirectly.

These contrasts are already indicated in Table 1, and further illustrated by Figure 1, showing significant differences in consumption and production of honey in selected countries.

Figure 1 presents a general pattern, though with some exceptions, where countries with high honey production also tend to have higher consumption. A comparison of Table 1

and Figure 1 indicates furthermore a possible relationship between a high honey production and a positive trade balance, as seen in Bulgaria, and Serbia. Conversely, countries with lower honey production, such as Germany, Italy, and the UK, are among those with the most negative trade balances.

The trade balance serves as a key indicator of the health of the honey market and, consequently, the thriving of the apiculture sector. Export and import figures are typically sourced from official trade statistics and are therefore considered more reliable than production and consumption data, notwithstanding discrepancies between Faostat and Eurostat figures.

On basis of Table 1, we can divide countries in 3 groups dependent on their annual trade balance per capita according to Faostat:

1. Positive trade balance: Bulgaria, Serbia, Türkiye
2. Slightly negative trade balance, between 0 and -0.25 kg honey per capita per year: Albania, Slovakia, Spain, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Denmark
3. Negative trade balance, under -0.25 kg honey per capita per year: Italy, Croatia, Germany, UK

Policies that directly influence markets comprise, for instance, trade agreements, subsidy programmes and competition policy. Examples of indirect policies are regulations on feed-stuffs, wages, energy, fertilisers, climate and environment. A clear link between policies and markets is not least the case for the European Union, which is concerned about the functioning of the internal market - see for instance Bahr (2024)¹³.

Direct EU regulation of the honey market happens via the Honey Directive⁴, latest amended in 2024 by the so-called Breakfast Directive¹⁴, which among other includes a definition of honey and requirements to its labelling. EU has enabled support to the beekeeping sector via the Common Agricultural Policy since 1997, whereas it has been mandatory for Member States to prioritise financial support to the sector since 2023¹⁵.

Typically, EU Member States as well as countries outside the EU, have a beekeeping law or a similar regulation, which has the role of recognising the sector and set some basic frames for its activities.

The objective of this research is to evaluate whether the observed market variations can be attributed to differences in policies, including legal frameworks within the countries under consideration, as well as budgetary allocations for sector support.

Online survey

Policies are basically aimed at regulating markets. On this basis, this article builds on opinions about policies that are either beneficial or detrimental for a thriving apiculture sector, and these policies are compared to some indicators for the health of the apiculture sector in that country.

Opinions about examples of promoting or deteriorating policies were collected via an online survey. In addition, an interview was made and selected literature also taken into consideration.

The online survey was made via Google Forms¹⁶. The survey comprised an introduction, where the purpose was explained, it was reminded what the meaning of policies are, and reference were made to prevailing GDPR rules and possibilities for clarification¹⁷. The introduction part made it possible to leave the name, e-mail address and organisational affiliation of the respondent, and it included the only obligatory field of the entire survey, namely what country the respondent was based in. Following that, there were three similar sections, where the respondent could write (freely) about a policy that was considered to promote the apiculture sector, and three sections, where the respondent could indicate policies that were considered to deteriorate the apiculture sector. It was possible on a voluntary basis to provide details, such as to indicate the type of the policy, provide a link to the specific policy, give a reference of the policy (law number or alike.), indicate the geographical scope, and indicate the impact of the policy (impact groups being aligned with the themes of the BeSafeBeeHoney work groups). None of the questions were compulsory, except as already mentioned, the country of the respondent.

Using Google forms means that the respondent could have an automated language translation of the survey, most accessible in case it was opened in a Chrome browser. Using Google Forms also means that management of the survey was facilitated by functions to register and edit survey questions, receive

email notifications every time a response was collected, view responses in a compiled format as well as individually, and download responses in comma separated file (.csv) format for further analyses.

The survey was launched at the first BeSafeBeeHoney conference, held in Larissa in Greece in the days 28–29 May 2024, where it was promoted in connection to the conference session on policies, and via a poster. A QR code was displayed at the poster and in a PowerPoint for introduction to the WG5 session of the conference, to make access to the survey as easy as possible. In addition, the survey was promoted via a newsletter, send to about 130 Work Group 5 members on 8 July and again on 13 September 2024.

Quantitative analysis of responses

15 answers were collected from respondents representing 12 European countries, and an interview-based response was additionally collected in one country. The countries are shown in [Figure 2](#), using the above definition of positive, slightly negative or negative honey trade balance.

For two countries, the response was empty or unclear, whereas three countries (Serbia, Bosnia & Herzegovina and Türkiye) each provided two responses. Thus, 72 policy examples were provided by 16 respondents from 13 countries¹, and [Table 2](#) shows, how these are distributed over issues and perceived positive or negative impact.

[Table 2](#) shows that more than 40% of responses relate to the issue of production systems and economy, whereas policies on abiotic and biotic stressors, disease and nutrition are seen as having less importance for a thriving apiculture sector. It can also be concluded that each respondent on average provided 4.5 examples of promotional or deteriorating policies, and that almost two thirds of the provided policy examples were perceived as having positive impact for the apiculture sector.

Using [Figure 2](#)'s division of responding countries, [Table 3](#) shows the division on number of promotional and deteriorating policy examples, collected with the survey.

33 policy examples were related to EU or other international policies.

A correlation between policies and trade balances would indicate a consistent pattern in which countries with negative trade balances reported more deteriorating policies, while those with positive trade balances would give more examples of promotional policies. However, [Table 3](#)'s quantitative analysis does not show any evidence of a relationship between annual trade balance per capita and the number of promotional or deteriorating policies.

¹ Kosovo is counted as a country in this respect, but neither Eurostat nor Faostat provides honey statistics for Kosovo.

Figure 2. Countries represented in responses to the policy survey, coloured according to the size of their honey trade balance: Dark orange – Positive trade balance, medium orange – slightly negative trade balance (from 0 to -0.25 kg per capita per year, light orange – negative trade balance (<-0.25 kg per capita per year).

Table 2. Survey responses, distributed over issues and perceived positive of negative impact.

Issue	Number of responses		
	Promotional policies	Deteriorating policies	Total
Abiotic stressors	4	8	12
Biotic stressors	3	2	5
Disease	8	1	9
Nutrition	7	7	14
Production systems & economy	24	8	32
In total	46	26	72

Qualitative analysis of responses

Since policy examples were collected using open questions, there are no identical responses, but there are responses that relate to the same issues:

- **Abiotic stressors**

Positive examples relate to EU policies, dealing with public support to information spreading (education, seminars), regulations that reduce the use of pesticides to a minimum. A Codex for Bee Products in Türkiye reduce the risk for chemicals to enter honey and other bee products.

Negative examples were given for non-EU countries, such as UK, where pesticides that were prohibited when UK was EU member, now are allowed again (e.g. neonicotinoids). For Serbia was mentioned non-restricted use and sale of antibiotics, that are used for plant disease treatment.

- **Biotic stressors**

As beneficial policy example was mentioned a national policy on the control/elimination of Asian Hornets (*Vespa velutina*), meaning that a rapid identification and location of attacks lead to appropriate disposal of Asian Hornets' nests and prevent or limit the spread of the Asian hornet (and associated detrimental effects on bees) across the UK.

Table 3. The number of promoting and deteriorating national policy examples for countries with positive, slightly negative and negative trade balance for honey, with averages per responding country shown in brackets.

	Number of responses (number of responses per responding country)		Comments
	Promotional policies	Deteriorating policies	
Positive	11 (5.5)	3 (1.5)	Three countries: Türkiye and Serbia - no national policies mentioned for Bulgaria
Slightly negative	11 (2.2)	6 (1.2)	Five countries: Bosnia & Herzegovina, Slovakia, Denmark, Spain and Albania
Negative	6 (3.0)	2 (1.0)	Four countries: Croatia and United Kingdom – Germany and Italy not mentioning national policies

- **Disease control**

Bosnia & Herzegovina and Croatia mentioned as example of positive policies that they have veterinarian legislation, that also cover measures to prevent, control and survey bee disease.

Of negative examples were from Danish side mentioned a private scheme to make combatting of the Varroa mite more efficient, but the frustration is that the scheme is ineffective since beekeepers cannot be sanctioned if they do not follow the scheme. Spain also mentions a parallel example of this policy defect.

- **Nutrition**

Some positive policy examples provided are not entirely clear since they refer to the Honey Directive, but it is not concerned about bee nutrition. Some examples see EU’s regulatory framework in support of biodiversity as positive, as well as EU’s Soil Mission, that would mean more healthy foraging possibilities for bees.

Of negative policy examples were for Bosnia & Herzegovina mentioned that inspection of honey is not anymore being a responsibility of veterinarian authorities. Another example pointed at the insufficiency of EU’s food regulations, since they alone concern about lead contamination of honey.

- **Production systems and economy**

Several examples of positive policies dealt with beekeepers’ access to subsidisation, for instance a subsidy per beehive in Serbia, an EU regulation making Member States’ subsidies of the apiculture sector mandatory, the possibility to use EU’s CAP funding for additional support to grow fallow fields with

flowers in Denmark, and support for bee queen purchase in Serbia.

Other positive examples mentioned the possibility for beekeepers to sell honey directly to consumers without formal business registration, EU’s quality schemes to protect products under different Designations of Origins, EU’s amendment of the Honey Directive to require the country of origin to be labelled on the honey, and beekeepers’ possibility to rent out beehives to crop producers and in this way generate income from pollination services.

Türkiye mentioned some beneficial policies, including a broad regulation aiming to ensure the sustainability of beekeeping by determining the principles regarding all kinds of production, breeding, accommodation, obtaining breeding material, fixed and migratory beekeeping, taking the necessary measures regarding the transportation of bee colonies, standardization of tools, machines and materials, development of honey plants agriculture, and training. The regulation covers issues related to project planning, queen bee breeding, artificial insemination of honeybees and registration of honeybee colonies.

Negative responses were mainly expressing a frustration of the lack of policies to avoid a suspected adulteration, specifically of imported honey. They also included a response that points at the lack of policies to counteract a demography of ageing beekeepers.

It is emphasised that the above points are not attempting to provide a complete overview of response, but alone to present some response examples.

To some extent, the survey responses overlap with policy issues that were captured by Foged (2024) from keynote

speeches at the BeSafeBeeHoney conference in Larissa in May 2024³. The issues listed in the referenced policy brief can be seen as identification of missing or failing policies dealing with the following:

- Ineffective measures to combat the Varroa mite – it was suggested to increase work for more genetic resistant bees and introduce more tight regulation on bee trade, including bee queen trade to avoid contamination.
- Insufficient regulation of use of pesticides and other chemicals – it was suggested to work for harmonising of the regulations for registration, trade and use of pesticides within all the EU to avoid farmers buying pesticides in neighbour countries that are illegal in their own country.
- Fraud and adulteration – it was recommended to work for better and more diverse labelling, including labelling for honeys' analysed content of nutraceutical constituents, stronger border control, and to introduce labelling that includes more detailed traceability information.

Conclusions and discussion

A quantitative analysis of 39 examples of policies that were associated with individual countries did not identify any correlation between a country's honey trade balance, measured as kilograms of honey per citizen per year, and the quality of its apiculture sector related policies.

Qualitative analysis of the survey responses, including 72 examples of policies, highlights three key policy issues perceived as most decisive for the quality of the honey market and its ability to sustain a thriving apiculture sector:

- First, subsidisation schemes are considered crucial for supporting the sector, with respondents noting that such policies can prioritise objectives including education and information dissemination, development initiatives, disease eradication programmes, and investment in beehives. Subsidisation is generally viewed positively, with explicit calls for increased funding. The expansion and mandatory financial support for the apiculture sector within the EU is widely regarded as beneficial.
- Second, there is a strong belief to the importance of enhanced product classification systems and accurate labelling, utilising reliable methods to verify label information with honey quality standards. These measures are considered necessary to combat fraud, promote fair competition, distinguish high-quality honey products rich in nutraceutical components, and reassure consumers about the absence of chemical residues. While this issue garners significant attention, effective laboratory methods for fraud detection have yet to be identified, while traceability

requirements may offer more feasible solutions to combat fraud.

- Third, concerns persist regarding overly permissive regulations governing the approval, registration, and use of veterinary medicines and pesticides, which may negatively impact the sector. Although EU regulations are generally regarded as superior to those outside the EU, there remains a need for harmonised regulations across EU Member States.

The policy survey provides valuable insights into apiculture sector policies regarded as either beneficial or detrimental to a sustainable honey market and the ongoing development of apiculture. Additionally, it highlights challenges within the sector resulting from irregular market mechanisms, with indications that the predominant market channels operate largely beyond public oversight, contributing to concerns about effective regulation and control.

The policy survey was spread via BeSafeBeeHoney project participants, mainly being researchers without primary concerns for policies, and being researchers having an inherent caution about sharing subjective opinions. The BeSafeBeeHoney project participants were for this reason encouraged to be helpful to obtain responses from beekeepers and especially beekeepers associations in their countries, since these are familiar with policies. At least two responses were given by representatives of beekeepers' associations, which is good, and also that a few other responses were provided by researchers, who are also beekeepers. Some of the responses were of limited quality and not sufficiently clear to include in the survey analysis.

Ideally, responses would have been obtained from beekeepers' associations in all of the more than 40 BeSafeBeeHoney countries; however, this was not achieved, and it is important to acknowledge the challenges of eliciting participation in online surveys. Nevertheless, given these constraints, we believe the survey responses are reasonably representative and comprehensive, supporting the validity of our conclusions for consideration in the European apiculture policy process.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data and software availability

Foged, H. L., Hoxha, F., & Majtan, J. (2025). Template and responses of policy survey. In Apiculture sector policies - positive and negative elements to support healthy market conditions (25 August 2025). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16941550>

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We sincerely appreciate the valuable input provided by all respondents, whose contributions form the foundation of this analysis.

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Open Peer Review

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Antonio de Jesus Cenobio-Galindo

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Following the evaluation of the manuscript, I present below some comments that require attention to consider the work for publication.

The title presents the study as a policy analysis; however, the document does not demonstrate that the elements are sufficient.

The abstract states that no differences were found between policies and trade balance; however, the survey design is inadequate to support any assessment, especially regarding representativeness across nations.

Regarding the previous comment, the research question cannot be adequately answered due to the methodological design.

The introduction lacks data relevant to the study, such as policies applied to the beekeeping sector or honey market regulations.

It is understood that the survey used open-ended questions, which prevents standardizing responses, hinders comparisons, and therefore does not allow for quantitative analysis.

Procedures for ensuring reliability or coding the data are not described.

It does not mention how incomplete or ambiguous responses were handled.

It is not mentioned whether participation bias was controlled for.

The results in Tables 2 and 3 show numbers, but there is no statistical analysis beyond the count.

The statements made in the results are based on perceptions.

The discussion in general is too brief and does not relate concepts that one would expect to see, such as adulteration in honey, informality in marketing channels, international trade.

The differences between countries and their geographical relevance are not explained.

The conclusions and discussions are not clearly differentiated from each other; likewise, in this section, the reader is not warned that the lack of correlation may be due to the design.

There are no recommendations, nor are the limitations of the work acknowledged.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

No

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

No

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

No

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

No

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

No

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

No

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: honey, stingless bees, food biotechnnology

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 18 Dec 2025

Henning Lyngsø FOGED

Thank you for your valuable review of our manuscript. Your comments are very useful for our amendment of the manuscript. You will in the "Notes to readers" find a general description of the revisions made. We understand that our original presentation of quantitative analyses, including trade balances for countries represented in responses, could be interpreted as a statistical analysis. We have consequently restructured the manuscript to stress that such analyses are alone done for the purpose of describing the dataset. We also moved these analyses away from the introduction since they are a part of the research and not background material. In this way we intend the manuscript to have a more logical and clear structure. We notice that you suggest the introduction to include an analysis of policies governing the sector. We stress, and have further substantiated how the manuscript is linked to the BeSafeBeeHoney project, which is funded by the EU, wherefore our geographical focus is Europe, where also the vast majority of BeSafeBeeHoney members are located. We do actually mention the main EU policies, including the Honey Directive, the Breakfast Directive, as well as the EU decision of making support to the sector compulsory via the CAP since 1997. We are not entirely clear on the comment that 'the introduction lacks data relevant to the study, such as policies applied to the beekeeping sector or honey market regulations,' and would appreciate more specific guidance on which aspects the reviewer considers insufficient or missing! We have noted your comment on "Procedures for ensuring reliability or coding the data are not described." To our understanding, reliability is of major relevance to consider when analysing data that are produced in a lab or similar, where observations are made, and you want to be ascertained that a solid calibration was ensured. For open-ended questions, we anticipate all

respondents provide different and subjective answers, and we don't want them to calibrate their answers with other respondents since that would lower the quality of the responses. Also, coding is typically something you do for large datasets of the same type as mentioned. However, we did some form of coding for the purpose of describing the policy examples given in the responses, namely in the following ways: 1) country, 2) positive or negative example, 3) the affiliation to the issue of the BeSafeBeeHoney work packages, 4) the countries trade balance, and 5) the policy type. Likewise, we would like to stress, that in a survey of the nature in question, there are no incomplete answers. There is no defined correct length of the text of an open-ended response. All questions are furthermore voluntary. Regarding the issue of ambiguity, we did not identify any ambiguous responses in our analysis: All responses were clear for us with respect to the mentioned 5 "codings" apart from the issue. There were examples of responses, which we did not understand, such as dealing with renewable energy, but since they were exceptional answers they have not had any effect on conclusions, which point at general patterns in raised policy issues. We would appreciate if you could provide specific examples from the published dataset where ambiguity is perceived that could affect our conclusions, so that we may address them appropriately. In addition, we emphasise, that by using open-ended questions, we do anticipate that all responses are "biased" and subjective, since there is no correct answer, and you cannot respond to such a survey like this in an objective and impartial way. The prerequisite is that respondents are affiliated in one or another way with the apiculture sector and are willing to express their opinions about the policies that influences the sector. Once again, we sincerely appreciate your comments. We acknowledge that the original version of the manuscript lacked sufficient clarity and logical structure. We hope that the revised version adequately addresses these issues. Should any concerns remain, we would be grateful for more detailed guidance on the specific points that require further improvement, taking into account the nature of our research.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 27 November 2025

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Małgorzata Dżugan

Uniwersytet Rzeszowski, Rzeszów, Poland

The topic addressed in this publication is extremely timely and valuable for the future of the beekeeping market, not only in EU countries. The authors attempted to determine which of the three policies: 1) strategies (implemented or planned), 2) regulations and regulatory standards, and 3) subsidy programs, survey respondents consider crucial for promoting the beekeeping sector. The research was conducted using open web-based survey. The methodology of such

research is based on two pillars: a well-prepared, well-thought-out survey questionnaire and a large number of responses (for proper statistical evaluation of observed trends).

In my opinion, both conditions were not met. The survey design does not ensure reliable responses; it relies on open-ended explanations and requires knowledge of the subject from the respondent. To avoid accidental errors, at least 100 surveys or a consensus position of a beekeeping organization in a given country should have been collected. The low survey response rate (16 in total) absolutely does not allow for correlation of the survey results with the annual trade balance of the honey market per capita. Furthermore, the conclusions should be preceded by a discussion of the results and constitute a summary of the whole publication. Therefore, I cannot recommend this work for indexing in its current form. Considering the informative value and importance of the topic for the health of the beekeeping sector and probably element of BeSafeBeeHoney COST project realization, I suggest the authors treat their study as preliminary and submit a Short communication that removes the above mentioned correlations and presents examples of policy implementation for the beekeeping sector in various EU countries. I encourage you to expand the group of survey respondents and include a more comprehensive explanation of the policy for the apiculture sector in the online questionnaires, e.g. in the form of a short video tutorial.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

No

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

No

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Honey and other bee product analysis - quality evaluation and using in apitherapy

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 18 Dec 2025

Henning Lyngsø FOGED

Thank you for your valuable review of our manuscript.

Your comments are very useful for our amendment of the manuscript. You will in the “Notes to readers” find a general description of the revisions made. In addition, we regret that our manuscript was not sufficiently clear and appreciate the opportunity to clarify, that our research did not intend to determine which of three policies respondents consider crucial for promoting the beekeeping sector. We have in various ways reformulated the manuscript to more clearly describe the objective of the research, especially in the formulation of the objectives. We are of the opinion, that using open ended questions for exploratory purposes does not require more than 100 responses, since it is not intended or even suited for statistical analysis, and we can assure that the design of the questionnaire was thoroughly considered. The methodological section emphasises now more clearly, also by use of a reference, that the use of open-ended questions is a recognised social-science method for exploring perceptions, that these are not meant for statistical analyses, but for qualitative analyses, and that each response is valuable and unique. We understand that our original presentation of quantitative analyses, including trade balances for countries represented in responses, could be interpreted as a statistical analysis. We have consequently restructured the manuscript to stress that such analyses are alone done for the purpose of describing the dataset. We also moved these analyses away from the introduction since they are a part of the research and not background material. In this way we intend the manuscript to have a more logical and clear structure.

Once again, we do appreciate you review comments. We acknowledge that the original version was of insufficient quality and not entirely clear and logically structured. We hope that the revised version adequately addresses your concerns. If any issues remain, we would appreciate further clarification of your specific concerns, given the scope and nature of our research.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 14 October 2025

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Ester Noguèr-Juncà

University of Lleida, Lleida, Spain

Dear Authors,

Thank you for the opportunity to review this work. While your paper offers valuable insights,

several critical issues remain unaddressed.

The originality of the research is not sufficiently established, particularly regarding its contribution to the existing literature and the research gap it aims to address.

The Introduction section is well-developed. Perhaps the explanation of BeSafeBeeHoney Project could be detailed.

One of the major weakness of the paper, in my view, lies in its methodology section. The number of surveys is insufficient to generalize the findings. It is necessary to add more information about the processes taken to ensure validity, reliability, and credibility of the results.

The Results section is well-developed, but the information could be detailed.

In my view, the Discussion and conclusion section represents another weak point of the paper.

It is necessary to create two separate sections. There is no connection between the discussion and the background.

The paper also lacks an explanation of its theoretical and practical contributions, as well as a discussion of its limitations and suggestions for future research directions.

The quality of communication and the use of English are adequate.

Given these limitations, I regret to inform you that I reject the manuscript in its current form.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

No

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

No

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: food tourism, food marketing, primary sector and tourism, tourism and gender

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 18 Dec 2025

Henning Lyngsø FOGED

Thank you for your valuable review of our manuscript. Your comments are very useful for our amendment of the manuscript. You will in the "Notes to readers" find a general description of the revisions made.

In addition, we acknowledge your concern that the original presentation might be interpreted as implying a statistical analysis of the survey responses, alike methods used in for instance biological research disciplines. We have in several ways amended the manuscript to clarify that this is not the intention: The methodological section emphasise more clear, that the data is collected by use of open-ended questions, which is a recognised social-science method for exploring perceptions, that these are not meant for statistical analyses, but for qualitative analyses, and that each response is valuable and unique. It is likewise stressed in the results section, that the three issues that were perceived as being most decisive for a thriving apiculture, were in fact dealt with in most of the responses, wherefore we do not feel that having additional responses would add substantial to the validity or representation of the conclusions. Also, it is now clearer that various quantification of the survey responses are alone having the purpose of describing the dataset. We hope that the amended manuscript cannot any more cause misunderstandings about the social science nature of our research and the use of open-ended questions for explorative purposes. Once again, we do appreciate you review comments. We acknowledge that the original version was of insufficient quality and not entirely clear and logically structured. However, we do hope that you are able to approve the revised version, and that you otherwise will explain in more detail what concerns you have, given the nature of our research.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.